

SmartSwim survey

This survey was conducted as part of a PhD project at EPFL to learn more about the analysis systems used by swimming coaches and clubs in Switzerland. It will take only 15 minutes of your time and your comments are very insightful for the rest of this project.

More information can be found on the following page:

<https://www.epfl.ch/labs/lmam/smart-swim/>

Thank you for your participation.

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* Required

Coach information

Please enter the following information about yourself.

1. Age

2. Gender

Mark only one oval.

Male

Female

Other

3. Sports

Check all that apply.

Competitive swimming

Triathlon

Other: _____

4. Coaching experience

How many years have you trained competitive swimmers as a profession?

Mark only one oval.

- 0-4
- 5-9
- 10-14
- 15-20
- More than 20 years

5. Your Email (if you want to know the survey results)

Swimming analysis systems

6. What analysis systems do you use for training? how frequently? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Daily	weekly	Monthly	Quarterly	Annually	Not at all
Camera (e.g. TEMPLO, GoPro)	<input type="radio"/>					
Force platform (e.g. KiSwim)	<input type="radio"/>					
Motion sensors (e.g. tritonwear, smartwatches)	<input type="radio"/>					
Heart rate monitor (e.g. Polar, Garmin)	<input type="radio"/>					
Blood lactate monitor	<input type="radio"/>					
Hand pressure sensor (e.g. Kz+)	<input type="radio"/>					
Tethered device (e.g. speedometer)	<input type="radio"/>					

7. Other systems?

8. Please mention the brands of the systems you use (if applicable)

9. In case you use cameras, how do you use them?

Mark only one oval.

- Only qualitative
- Qualitative and quantitative
- Only quantitative
- Other: _____

10. When do you prefer to observe the analysis results?

Mark only one oval.

- During the training (real-time)
- After each lap
- After the training session
- Other: _____

11. Please mention the "Advantages" of your swimming analysis system(s).

Check all that apply.

- Ease of use
- Accurate results
- Quick feedback
- Easy to understand results
- Other: _____

12. Please mention the "Disadvantages" of your swimming analysis system(s).

Check all that apply.

- Time-consuming
- Inaccurate
- Need a lot of effort
- Difficult to understand results
- Not detailed enough
- Other: _____

Important parameters to track

If you use any swimming analysis system, what parameters do you follow?
If you don't use any, which parameters do you find essential and useful? Consider the four competitive styles (front crawl, breaststroke, butterfly and backstroke) when answering the questions.

- The parameters are categorized in four classes:
- 1- General parameters
 - 2- Start parameters
 - 3- Strokes parameters
 - 4- Turn parameters

General performance analysis

13. 1- General parameters

Check all that apply.

- Lap average velocity
- Lap time and lap count
- Total distance
- Heart rate and calories
- Other: _____

Start performance analysis

14. 2- Start parameters

Please select the start parameters that you track (or you want to track)

Check all that apply.

- Push off/dive maximum velocity/acceleration
- Angles (water entry angle, body posture, etc.)
- Push/jump duration
- Jump length, maximum depth, etc.
- Ondulation number of kicks and kick rate
- Ondulation average velocity/acceleration
- Start kinetics (push/dive force, power, etc.)
- Other: _____

Strokes performance analysis

15. 3- Strokes parameters

Please select the strokes parameters that you track (or you want to track)

Check all that apply.

- Average velocity/acceleration (per stroke and all strokes)
- Counts and rates (stroke/breath/kick count & rate)
- Performance irregularity (motion/velocity/acceleration variability, etc.)
- Distance per stroke
- Arms positioning and stroke phases (pull, push, etc.)
- Body pitch and roll angles
- Time per stroke
- Stroke kinetics (arms/legs propulsion, power, etc.)
- Other: _____

Turn performance analysis

16. 4- Turn parameters

Please select the turn parameters that you track (or you want to track)

Check all that apply.

- Turn time
- Push maximum velocity/acceleration
- Turn rotation velocity
- Time for 5m before wall to 10m after
- Other: _____

Motion sensors for training

17. Motion sensors for swimming *

Are you interested in using motion sensors (such as Triton) in training sessions?

Mark only one oval.

Yes, I use them for training (I think they are useful for training).

No, I've never used them.

18. If "No", why?

Check all that apply.

I've never heard of them

Too difficult to use

Not comfortable to use for the swimmer

High cost

Low accuracy

Useless results

Other: _____

19. If "Yes", please mention the brand. What weaknesses/ strengths did you notice when using the device?

20. How much can you (your club) pay for such a sensor for each swimmer in a year? *

Mark only one oval.

- <50 CHF
- 50-100 CHF
- 100-150 CHF
- 150-200 CHF
- >200 CHF
- I don't know

SmartSwim
solution

Here is our solution!

A smart swimming suit with a sensor integrated on lower back of the swimmer in a small pocket. You just turn on the sensor and use it during the training session. It provides a full performance analysis after the end of the session.

What does SmartSwim provide?

SmartSwim provides the following for each swimmer in a training session:

- 1- General parameters (swimming (in each style) and rest time, swim distance, total average velocity, etc.).
- 2- Detection of all swimming laps (wall to wall)
- 3- Detection of swimming phase (dive/push, glide, undulation, strokes and turn) and give a phase-based analysis:
 - Left: The performance evaluation chart shows the goal metrics for swimming laps (for example L1 to L5), the average performance (light green) and the best performance (dark green).
 - Right: The stroke average velocity chart shows the average velocity per stroke during swimming laps and velocity variation in the legend.
- 4- And more details on each swimming phase (sacrum angles and accelerations, stroke efficiency, etc.)

SmartSwim phase-based analysis

21. How do you grade using a sensor on lower back from 1 to 5 in the following aspects? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
Comfortable on swimmer body	<input type="radio"/>				
Practical to use in training sessions	<input type="radio"/>				

22. In general, do you find this device useful for training? considering the sensor location and the parameters it provide. *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, it seems easy to use and provides valuable parameters.
- No, it is not appropriate for training.

23. If "Yes", how frequently you will use it?

Mark only one oval.

- Every session
- Once a week
- Before competitions
- Once every season
- Other: _____

24. If "No", what are the issues with this idea? please help us improve the idea.

End of the survey

Thank you very much for your time and participation.
Your answers are insightful for us.

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